

Prospective Synergy Between Bangladeshi SMEs and Smart City: Through the Lens of Society 5.0

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Abstract. Rapid urbanization in the emerging markets necessitates utilizing the scarce resources more reasonably and sustainably, for which technology adaptation is imperative. Despite this, the emerging markets suffer from weak technology and lag from realizing entrepreneurial opportunities inspired by a human-centric concept of Society 5.0. The key research aim is twofold. First, to explore the possibilities of transforming the emerging markets into smart cities in Bangladesh. Second, the potential of introducing and operating Smart SMEs in the smart cities as a pre-condition to embrace Society 5.0 for ultimate wellbeing for humans across the emerging economy. The study adopts a clustered content analysis method, followed by collection and classification of the relevant extant literature on the urbanization status of Bangladesh, Smart City, and Society 5.0. The literature review suggests that, with the right digital solutions, Society 5.0 may inspire to build a more versatile set of SMEs of the future: Smart SMEs. The study formulates a framework addressing Society 5.0-inspired Smart City's potentials in the emerging markets to create Smart SMEs. The study pioneers in offering Smart SMEs approach to fit in the concept and proposes a new definition of 'Smart City' based on its rapport with emerging markets. The study foresees a meaningful implementation of Society 5.0 to create transformational value among other emerging Asian nations, including Bangladesh. New directions of future research to empirically test the connections to address diverse social and human needs are also suggested by the study.

Keywords: Smart City, SMEs, Society 5.0.

1 Introduction

On the edge of Industry 4.0, the Emerging Markets (EM) have turned into melting pots for entrepreneurs. The vision of creating a more equitable, livable, and sustainable world has led the researchers to accentuate the multidisciplinary approaches of EM [1]. Urbanization in the EM is among the critical processes that deal with the urban concentration of the population. The exponentially growing city-based population must adapt to EM's technology for using scarce resources more reasonably and sustainably. The

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competitive edge of a city often is reflected by its novelty and economic sustainability. The cities from the emerging markets have been implementing ICT and other networked infrastructure to ensure more incredible business growth among the SMEs and the large incumbents to stay competitive. This competitive move leads to more significant entrepreneurial activity in a Smart City [2].

With better flexibility and adaptability, SMEs can play a critical role in boosting productivity and economic growth and equalize income distribution [3] in the urbanized economy. Those emerging markets often embellish the concept of Smart City [4], which has been acknowledged as highly entrepreneurial by scholars and policy-makers [5]. The nexus between city-based economy and entrepreneurship remaining multidirectional, the SMEs complements well with the smart cities [6]. Nevertheless, an analysis of SMEs' interaction and emerging economies, especially from Bangladesh's perspective, has been missing. This paper seeks to address the research gap by observing this relationship from the lens of Society 5.0, a human-centric approach for economic advancement. The study aims to address the social needs, which is a timely research-requirement.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Urbanization in Emerging Markets

Emerging Markets (EM) denotes a developing economy that progresses to a futuristic industrial economy from an agricultural and resource-dependence economy often followed by the industrial revolution. EM is characterized by unique features such as vast disparity of growth rates in urban and rural market growth rates, the evolution of socio-cultural trends, the emergence of bureaucratic and corrupted systems, and diffusion of innovations. Given the distinctive challenges and opportunities, EM is substantially differentiated from the developed markets. By investing in education, infrastructure, defense, social programs, EM aims for creating faster GDP growth, greater connection with global markets, and a better standard of living [7].

On the other hand, urbanization in the EM refers to a social process that triggers the urban cities to grow and the societies to adopt city-based lifestyles and culture with the migration of the population from rural to urban areas. Global urbanization is led by the rise of city-based world population from 30 percent in the 1950s to 50 percent in 2011. It is predicted to rise to 70 percent before 2050, according to the United Nations report (2012), and this is more prevalent among the emerging and developing economies [5]. In 2020, the urban-dwellers were 38.2 percent of the population of the developing and emerging country, Bangladesh. The urban population is growing at a 1.9 percent rate [8]. Despite the faster urbanization in Bangladesh compared to the other South Asian countries between 2000 and 2010 [9], the country has experienced messy urbanization, with some 47 percent of the urban population belongs to slums [10]. In terms of the 2020 global livability index, Dhaka has been positioned as the 3rd among the worst cities [11] [12].

To overcome rapid urbanization challenges, including resource-scarcity and infrastructural inadequacy [13], SMEs can enhance their GDP contribution. To realize the value and potentials of SMEs in Industry4.0, adopting new technologies is imperative.

SME entrepreneurs need to emphasize updating their technical and data-related skills to operate in dynamic and competitive environments. At the global level, about one-third of the skills are subject to be obsolete following the skill-disruption trends over the next half-decade [14]. The universities, SMEs, corporations, and citizens should enthusiastically participate in the skill up-gradation process. It can be inferred that a successful implementation of smart cities will work as a catalyst of SME development in Bangladesh's emerging economy.

The recent trends indicate the readiness of Bangladesh to create emerging markets. Besides standing as the fastest growing economy of the Asia-Pacific; stable governance and policies regarding taxation, economic, and foreign trade, the low-cost labor, and a gradual shift towards information and communication technology (ICT) industry and renewable power sources have played a significant role in forming its economic foundation [15]. Consequently, the mobile-friendly internet connection is accessible to general people with 4G internet since 2018, which is expected to reach 51 percent by 2025 [16]. Another critical aspect of smart cities is cashless to ensure efficiency [17]. To convert more than 70 percent of Bangladesh's unbanked population [18] to cashless, mobile financial services are contributing to creating financial inclusion [19] among 50 million users, followed by a rise in mobile application-based services.

These changes make the lives of the users easier and prove to be a source of employment for Bangladesh's workforce. Another commendable act by the government of Bangladesh is the increased incentive (20-45 percent duty) to use fuel-efficient and environment-friendly hybrid cars instead of regular ones (100-300 percent duty) [20]. In the emerging markets, smart cities' creation will enhance urbanization and make the cities more livable [4]. As a consequence of such a digital revolution with urbanization, the Smart City concept's interest has grown immensely. The information and communication technologies (ICT), policies based on high-tech infrastructures, and city-dwellers efforts to enhance the quality of lives have improved possibilities for cities to organize urban growth [2].

2.2 Smart City in Emerging Markets

A visionary goal of emerging markets to become a Smart City or even a Super-smart City leads the emerging markets' entrepreneurs to adopt robust and prudent means to use technology. The governments of many emerging markets have been progressing to create smart cities. Some 26 megacities from the largest emerging markets in the ASEAN region, including Singapore, Java, Bangkok, Jakarta, and Manila, have adopted the smart city concept, and most of them have started to experience the significant value of their investments already [4]. Therefore, the term 'smart city' has turned into a trailblazer that could be adopted in renovating the emerging markets. Nevertheless, the concept remains a fuzzy buzzword [21]. Some related terminologies such as eco-city, sustainable city, digital city, intelligent city, or knowledge city are often analogous to the concept. The concept's reasons to lack unanimity are that most of the definitions are centered on either technology or smart human-resources or smart collaboration between government and citizens [22], or even customer-centricity [4]. The following Table 1 offers different perspectives offered by various authors on the concept.

Table 1. Different Perspectives of Smart City.

Authors	Viewpoints of various authors
Giffinger et al. (2007)	A forward-looking and well-performing city with a set of intelligent features including people, environment, living, agility, governance, and economy, built by self-decisive and conscious citizens [23].
Caragliu et al. (2011)	A city that invests in human capital, social capital, traditional infrastructure, and modern communication infrastructure (ICT) and manages natural resources with participatory governance to fuel economic sustainability and quality of life [24].
Lombardi et al. (2012)	A city that generates intellectual capital, wealth, and regulations for university, industry, civil society, and government while stimulating the abilities of presupposition and knowledge-transmission as a prerequisite to innovation systems [25].
Bakici et al. (2013)	A city that actively generates innovative ideas by nurturing clusters and promoting 'living labs of competent citizens to co-create products or services [26].
Richter, Karus & Syrja (2015)	A clustered area of high concentration of novel knowledge by creative citizens and institutions and implementing a digital infrastructure aims to achieve economic sustainability and high quality of life concerning natural resources scarcity [5].
Lara et al. (2016)	A domain consisting of smart concepts including technology, transport-system, health-service, governance, and economy [27].
Angelidou (2017)	It promotes various phenomena, including technology-centric, human resources and entrepreneurs, information security, privacy, social status, management, networking, strategic framework, interdisciplinary arrangement, and generic collaboration [28].

The collaboration of private players, people, and policy-makers is a mandatory prerequisite to positively impacting smart cities [29]. The creative citizens often turn themselves to visionary entrepreneurs with IoT-based infrastructure [30]. Smart cities offer avenues for creativity, innovation [31], and entrepreneurial opportunities, followed by the profound rise of consumption and production patterns. While the ICTs and other network infrastructure direct the SMEs to realize new opportunities, they create new markets [32] and commercialize new ideas [29]. The policy-makers, corporate entrepreneurship [33], and citizen-led enterprises [30] play an enriched role in converting the emerging market into Smart City. Features specific to smart cities, including big data or open data, would foster open governance, accountability, transparency, citizen engagement, and economic progress. The infrastructure and entrepreneurial opportunities [34] and greater access to data lead to the uninterrupted creation of new firms [25] and turns the cities into seedbeds for innovation and entrepreneurship [5].

Nevertheless, as the emerging markets such as Bangladesh are still lagging due to the absence of a feeble technology-base to realize the Smart City concept fully, necessary policies should be introduced to accentuate protecting citizens' rights so that technology never supersedes humanity [20]. Therefore, a human-centered approach is what the emerging markets need to add to the Smart City approach.

2.3 Society 5.0

The most enhanced version of contemporary and human-centric society is Society 5.0, which emerged as Japan's strategic national political initiative to balance technological instruments of big data, AI, IoT, and robotics with economic growth resolve societal issues [35] [36]. It seeks to improve productivity via the digitization and redesign of business models and simultaneously builds society with innovation and globalization [37]. Society 5.0 is a process of value-addition to industrial and societal aspects [38]. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that focus on attaining sustainable humanity by mitigating their social problems complement Society 5.0.

To succeed, Society 5.0 needs to accentuate human control by integrating innovation policy (government), entrepreneurial spirit, and skills (civic society and innovative institutions) [39]. The transformation is expected to help humans live their lives easier and faster, greatly assisted by technology. Business transformation is accelerated by and built upon digital technologies and supports the businesses' experience more remarkable growth. Japanese Robotics market is anticipated to stand at USD 87 billion in 2035 from a mere USD 9 billion in 2010. Many Asian countries, including Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, are aiming towards a new human-centered society [40].

3 Methodology

The study objective is to address the nexus between SMEs and Smart City to create pre-conditions for Society 5.0 for humans' ultimate wellbeing. The study conducts an extensive review of the current literature, and the process is consistent with Richter et al. (2015) [5]. The study specifically seeks to understand the impact between SMEs and Smart City (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Prospective Synergic Effect of Smart City among the SMEs.

A clustered content analysis method has been adopted as the study aims to investigate a research-domain that is not yet systematically studied. Based on the existing literature, the study will use a method to advance understanding of the phenomenon

and open up research avenues. A comprehensive analysis of Smart City's three-dimensional themes, SME 5.0, and the urbanization and economic status of Bangladesh has been conducted. The most relevant literature, published articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters have been considered for this purpose. Since the Smart City is an emerging yet trans-disciplinary approach with no established research-base, various management, economics, and business journals were considered accentuating urban communications, urban technology, and human resources. The present review was conducted in three stages [2]:

1. Searching of articles through Emerald, Google Scholar, ProQuest, and Web of Science databases using a set of search phrases such as "Society 5.0", "smart cit*", "SME and Urban Cit*" and "Bangladesh urban econom*" to identify relevant sources of information until 2021. The peer-reviewed articles were the prime focus.
2. Classification of the articles by further narrowing down the data set. It was ensured that those data set contains either of the terms, such as *entrepreneur*, *firm*, *SME*, *small business*. The stage further furnishes two different sets of articles on entrepreneurship (SMEs) and smart cities.
3. Clustered content analysis was conducted to explore emerging markets' entrepreneurial context to understand SMEs' influence on smart cities. The insights of the articles were divided into three distinct research-streams: (a) Urbanization, (b) Emerging Markets, and (c) Smart cities.

4 Discussion

4.1 SMEs through the lens of Society 5.0

To ensure human-centered problem-solving and value creation, a smooth merging of the "people with things" and the "real with virtual" worlds is necessary. This fuse will lead to transformational advances to various prolonged societal problems prevailing in the emerging economies. All related stakeholders of economic growth across the globe, including the governments and firms, anticipate the smart urbanization and technological changes will continue to trigger a positive environment for adopting Society 5.0 within the next few years by the emerging markets, which have been experiencing synchronized and real-time revolutions from the industrial and urban aspects. These revolutions accompanied by increased inter-relations and intra-relations among people and data will accelerate technological advancements. The robust shift towards the digital age has been occurring ten times faster and three hundred times the scale of the Industrial Revolution's societal transformation, leaving some three thousand times impact on human lives [41].

Society 5.0 can be a suitable catalyst to renovate and upgrade SMEs by empowering them to enhance the quality of life instead of just boosting technology's impact. Various concepts such as big data, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence are anticipated to convert to pearls of new wisdom through the process. Such revolution is necessary to create corridors of humanity and equity [42]. The possibilities created by the Japanese phenomenon are expected to address individual needs and resolve social problems from diverse-levels. As a result of its significant influence, the other Asian nations, including Bangladesh, can be hopeful to experience Japan's super-smart society's

transformational benefits, and the citizens may lead their lives easier, better and faster. To better respond to the challenges imposed by the messy urbanization and provide a tailored solution to the customers in the emerging economies, the citizens deserve a thorough understanding of smooth transition towards Smart City's concept with the light of Society 5.0 [43].

4.2 Potentials of Smart SMEs in Bangladesh

SMEs, as the economic backbone of an economy, enhances sustainable industrialization and employment. The contagion of the COVID-19 presents a significant threat to the SMEs of Bangladesh, requiring interdependencies among business, nature, education, and society to develop a readiness to operate, grow, and survive in the post-covid economy [44]. With a greater approachability towards financial sources, social and professional networks, or entrepreneurial capital, the emerging markets can be expressed as smart cities for a one-stop-solution to innovation, productivity, humanity, and equity. The high-end resources, production factors, and the supply chain network's intellectual capital have remained conducive to business growth. The favorable business-environment further reinforces Smart City's competent vehicle-set, including the regulatory institutions, training establishments, public transportation, and healthcare [13]. Also, to be more responsive to citizens, the smart cities may adopt a quadruple-helix model, where (a) the government by allocating resources and planning policies, (b) corporations and universities by creating more experience, expertise, and know-how, (c) SMEs by initiating small-scale social improvements, and (d) the smart citizens by addressing various issues to resolve sustainably [30] [45].

Given the correlation between SMEs and emerging markets, the present study suggests a revised definition of Smart City: "a concept that instigates productivity, sustainability, equity, and livability among the citizens by giving them a voice and among the creative entrepreneurs by giving them opportunities to use digital infrastructure, all while keeping in mind about resource-limitation". If Smart City's concept is applied adequately and correctly in Bangladesh, the higher spatial and contextual proximity among the ventures will lead to knowledge spillovers. This implementation may effectively open the corridor to commercialization opportunities of innovation. The scenario, in turn, would lead to tremendous business growth and an 'innovative spirit' [46] among the SMEs. With the right digital solutions offered by the Smart City, the SMEs would be better able to fine-tune the 'innovative spirit', scale up their businesses, respond to the dynamic customer demands, and build a more versatile set of SMEs: Smart SMEs [40].

A combination of ICT, business-led urban development, government, and policy-makers will turn the Smart City of Bangladesh into a center of entrepreneurship and homeland of Smart SMEs [26]. Also, by acknowledging the resource-limitation of the urban cities of Bangladesh, the characteristics of social and environmental sustainability of Smart City will help create entrepreneurial opportunities for the Smart SMEs [2]. For the Smart SMEs to be effective, the Smart City must complement the knowledge-intensive sectors such as creative and tech-based industries. Also, as the knowledge-creating networks are primarily based on transferring and adopting tacit knowledge, the Smart City should connect with 'living labs' consisting of highly-educated

entrepreneurs [47]. The capital city Dhaka and port cities such as Chittagong, Khulna, and Sylhet offer more forward-looking possibilities for Bangladesh's economic activities and are among the fore-runners to embrace the Smart City concept.

4.3 Realizing Society 5.0 by Smart SMEs

To add value and realize the concept of Society 5.0 of a human-centric growth strategy, the entrepreneurs need to generate quality data first. By ensuring effective rapport between cyberspace and physical space [48], the Smart SMEs and Society 5.0 can be catalysts to each other. The growth of Smart SMEs can lead to market creation and economic development for smart cities. By realizing the benefits of Society 5.0 and operating in the smart cities, the limitations associated with spatial, socio-cultural, and financial factors are expected to reduce. Also, adopting innovative business models would trigger economic growth. Thereby the scope of Smart SMEs would be heightened in the emerging markets of Bangladesh [49].

For a resource-scarce economy like Bangladesh, rather than aiming to create unicorn startups with exponential-growth, dominating, and competitive attitudes, as coined by Aileen Lee in 2013 [50], the smart SMEs should emphasize being zebra SMEs that are sustainable, mutualistic, and promoters of social wellbeing with regenerative growth [51]. Initiated by four women entrepreneurs, as mentioned in the book named, "Starting a Revolution: what we can learn from female founders about the future of business" [52], the 'zebra movement' can be an excellent example for the women-owned SMEs as well. Smart SMEs are expected to arch their massive impact in the urban economy, being empowered by the big data revolution. Also, tapping into a rising consciousness among all the stakeholders, the SMEs could better tackle socio-economic challenges coinciding with the SDGs.

5 Conclusion

Being crucial actors and architects of the future Smart City in Bangladesh's emerging markets, the SMEs should make a conscious and continuous effort to collaborate the social and business welfares. By embracing technology and networked infrastructural makeover, the SMEs can turn to tomorrow's Smart SMEs to address the citizens and society. The values and promises of Society 5.0 are expected to eradicate the gaps associated with gender, language, culture, and region and address individual needs from diverse-levels. The SMEs being flexible, competent, and versatile sectors of the economy, can serve as catalysts towards an extraordinary digital transformation. Effective utilization of Smart SMEs will lead to greater sustainability of the smart cities. Considering the strong interdependences between Smart City and SMEs, detailed empirical studies to examine the association between various variables of the two domains from the emerging counties' context are suggested. Also, a continued review study may be conducted to offer recommendations to reduce the barriers to implement the Smart City concept in the light of Society 5.0.

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